

Belief dynamics and directed technical progress as drivers of a green transition? An agent-based exploration

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Abstract

Green transitions are desirable or even necessary in most fields of economic activity, and current research is investigating their potential in many sectors. However, at the theoretical level, the economic mechanisms underlying the feasibility of green transitions are underexplored. In this article, we analysed an abstract agent-based model that builds on the classical Ramsey growth model. We consider an economy with two capital stocks that differ in terms of greenhouse gas emissions but are otherwise substitutes. With technical progress through learning by doing, and with a “brown” capital stock that starts at a higher level of technical progress, a single benevolent planner has no incentive to invest in the “green” capital stock. Considering intertemporal utility maximiser agents leads to several mathematical difficulties. Therefore, we develop an agent-based model in which the driving mechanism behind green investment is an opinion dynamics process which represents whether or not agents switch to green capital. The paper explores different settings in the formulation of the opinion dynamics along the economic process and finds that beliefs toward green investment are internal mechanisms that could drive a green transition. How fast and when the agents’ beliefs change indicates whether a green transition would occur or not.

Keywords: Agent-based model, Directed technical progress, Belief dynamics, Green Growth, Green transitions, Climate Change

JEL Classification: C63 , D83 , D91 , O33 , O44

1 Introduction

Climate change, as one of the main challenges humanity is facing in the 21st century, calls for formulating sustainable pathways towards a green economy, resulting “in improved well-being and social equity while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities” (UNEP, 2011). Across the mainstream economic literature, several efforts have been undertaken to find ways to align economic growth with environmental sustainability. To name just a few examples, [Lans Bovenberg and Smulders \(1995\)](#) investigate how pollution-augmenting technological change can be managed to achieve sustainable growth and [Acemoglu et al \(2012\)](#) highlight how technological change can be directed towards environmentally friendly innovations. More recently, [Jin et al \(2021\)](#) address how to solve the issue of capital stranding in a transition to clean energy. Next to more standard economic models, also simulation models are employed in this context; for instance, [Lamperti et al \(2020\)](#) explore green transition dynamics to low carbon energy technologies using an agent-based model. In these works, external factors influence agents to transition to a sustainable pathway and a need for well-defined policies to steer technological innovation and economic activities towards a green economy is emphasised.

In the policy-related literature, there are several narratives relating to the aim of shifting the economy to a more sustainable pathway ([Belmonte-Ureña et al, 2021](#)). One of the most debated among these is Green Growth (see, e.g. [Fouquet \(2019\)](#)). It outlines economic growth while decreasing greenhouse gas emissions to protect the environment ([OECD, 2011](#)). However, in the Green Growth literature, theoretical foundations for understanding underlying mechanisms are insufficient ([Polewsky et al, 2024](#)).

In this paper, we investigate belief dynamics as a possible internal mechanism to explain a change of behaviour towards green investment at the agent level, and how this behavioural change can lead to a green (growth) transition. Opinion dynamics¹ is a well-studied human process (see for instance [Castellano et al, 2009](#); [Galesic et al, 2021](#), and references therein). There is a nascent literature that integrates opinion dynamics processes into economic agent-based models to understand how public opinion evolves and influences policy decisions in the context of climate change (for a detailed review see [Lackner et al, 2024](#)). To our knowledge, however, it has not been investigated what kind of role these processes could play in driving a green transition.

In this paper, we consider versions of a stylized agent-based model, building on previous works by [Steudle et al \(2018\)](#) and [Figueroa Alvarez and Wolf \(2024b\)](#). The former paper investigates the possibilities of green growth in an agent-based Ramsey growth model structure with three additional building blocks: endogenous technical change, directed technical change, and a labour market with search. Considering just two-time steps, it provides a proof of concept that an economy populated by many agents can find itself in a coordination game – in addition to the conventional equilibrium, this features a “green” equilibrium with higher growth and lower unemployment. The latter paper extends the model from the former one to a dynamic setting with

¹As is customary in the opinion and belief dynamics literature, we also refer to beliefs as opinions.

more than two-time steps but explores just the first building block: endogenous technical change. Different types of agents are defined according to the information they have about endogenous technical change. An economy of “collaborative” agents that emulate the representative benevolent planner can reproduce the optimal growth path from standard models. “Ignorant” agents, that disregard their contribution to technical progress – as is usually assumed in the literature – obtain a lower growth path since the externality of technical progress is not internalized. “Witty” agents do consider their contribution to technical change, implying that they need expectations on the other agents’ investment to optimize their utility. However, if a witty agent is small compared to the overall economy, it is hardly distinguishable from the ignorant agent (Figuroa Alvarez and Wolf, 2024b). Therefore, we will consider the simpler ignorant agents here.

These agents are called “farms” because they combine activities usually attributed to firms (production) and households (consumption). Along the lines of a Ramsey growth model, they maximise their intertemporal utility under the usual conditions: the produced good is used for consumption and investment and the capital stock evolves through depreciation and investment. We use standard functional forms, for example, a Cobb-Douglas production function. In the production process, we further assume endogenous technical progress through learning-by-doing, that is, a labour-augmenting technical progress factor evolves with capital growth. As for the utility function, we consider the natural logarithm, where utility is derived solely from consumption; that is, there is no disutility of labour. To keep the model simple all agents have a constant labour amount of 1 – we leave a labour market model to future work. Here, we add a differentiation of the production process into a “brown”, conventional technology that produces greenhouse gas emissions and a “green” one that is considered clean or environmentally friendly. While farms are similarly myopic as in the two previously described works, in that they consider only the current and one future time step in their utility optimization, here we add a more forward-looking component by incorporating a cognitive element into the farms, i.e. the farms have beliefs that define their environmental attitude, and in consequence, shape their behaviour as to whether they invest in green or brown capital.

The underlying setting is defined in Section 2. Then, Section 3 shows that there is no room for initializing a transition away from the brown and towards a green economy in standard models with myopic agents.

Therefore, we include a longer-term perspective that allows agents to expect a transition to green technology in the long run. The concepts behind the underlying driving mechanisms are introduced in Section 4. With these, in Section 5, we define an agent-based model in which agents can switch to green investment and phase out brown production. Results from this model are investigated in Section 6, and Section 7 concludes.

2 The setting

To investigate theoretical implications impeding, neutral, or leading to a possibility of green transitions, we consider a very basic Ramsey growth model setting with

endogenous technical progress (learning-by-doing) and two capital stocks. We denote the two capital stocks B (brown) and G (green capital) and the respective levels of technical progress β and γ . In a time-step t , an agent, indexed by i , needs to take two decisions: its total amount of labour $L_t^{(i)}$ has to be allocated to the two production processes such that $b_t^{(i)} + g_t^{(i)} = L_t^{(i)}$, and it has to take investment decisions for the two capital stocks, where investments are denoted $I_B^{(i)}$ and $I_G^{(i)}$, respectively. Its consumption at time t is denoted $C_t^{(i)}$ and utility gained from consumption by $U^{(i)}$. With the usual assumptions outlined in the Introduction, farm i faces the following optimization problem:

$$\max_{I_G^{(i)}, I_B^{(i)}, g_t^{(i)}, g_{t+1}^{(i)}} U^{(i)} = \ln(C_t^{(i)}) + \rho \ln(C_{t+1}^{(i)}), \quad (1)$$

subject to

$$P_T^{(i)} = (G_T^{(i)})^\alpha (\gamma_T g_T^{(i)})^{1-\alpha} + (B_T^{(i)})^\alpha (\beta_T b_T^{(i)})^{1-\alpha} \quad \text{for } T = t, t+1 \quad (2)$$

$$g_T^{(i)} + b_T^{(i)} = L_T^{(i)} = 1 \quad \text{for } T = t, t+1 \quad (3)$$

$$C_t^{(i)} = P_t^{(i)} - I_G^{(i)} - I_B^{(i)} \quad (4)$$

$$G_{t+1}^{(i)} = (1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} + I_G^{(i)} \quad (5)$$

$$B_{t+1}^{(i)} = (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)} + I_B^{(i)} \quad (6)$$

$$C_{t+1}^{(i)} = P_{t+1}^{(i)} \quad (7)$$

$$\gamma_{t+1} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n G_{t+1}^{(j)}}{\sum_{j=1}^n G_t^{(j)}} \gamma_t \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_{t+1} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n B_{t+1}^{(j)}}{\sum_{j=1}^n B_t^{(j)}} \beta_t \quad (8)$$

Here, Equation (1) shows the myopic maximisation that takes into account only the present and one future time step. Equation (2) defines the Cobb-Douglas production function using the respective capital stocks and labour, where the latter is augmented by the corresponding technical progress values; the total production is the sum of production from the two processes. Equation (3) indicates that the given amount of labour ($L_T^{(i)} = 1$ for simplicity) has to be allocated to the two production processes. While at time t , production is used for both consumption and investments (see Equation (4)), at time $t+1$, no future investment is considered (Equation (7)). Equations (5) and (6) describe the evolution of the capital stocks through depreciation and investment, and the equations in (8) define the evolutions of technical progress through learning by doing in a system with n farms.

An assumption that shall be made throughout is that the system starts in a state where the brown capital stock is larger and the green technology is comparatively new. Hence, $\beta_0 \gg \gamma_0$ in a system that is otherwise symmetric in its structure for the two sectors.

3 Difficulties with a standard growth model approach

Intuitively, given that $\beta_0 \gg \gamma_0$, agents will have no incentive to start investing in the green, much less productive technology in the very myopic setting outlined above. This will be briefly illustrated in Section 3.1 for the simplest case of a representative agent. Posing that, for whatever reason, agents do start investing in green technology after all, Section 3.2 illustrates further difficulties that arise for the myopic optimization. This sets the scene for considering driving mechanisms behind green investment that lie outside a rational agent's Ramsey-model-like optimization scheme (Section 4).

3.1 A representative agent

For a representative agent in the closed economy laid out above, a single agent holds the total capital of both types: brown $B = \sum_j^n B^{(j)}$ and green $G = \sum_j^n G^{(j)}$. Hence, the levels of technical progress are determined by this agent's capital stocks

$$\beta_{t+1} = B_{t+1} \frac{\beta_t}{B_t} \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_{t+1} = G_{t+1} \frac{\gamma_t}{G_t}$$

so that the production function can be rewritten along the lines of an AK model, as

$$B_{t+1}^\alpha (b_{t+1} \beta_t)^{1-\alpha} = B_{t+1}^\alpha \left(B_{t+1} \frac{\beta_t}{B_t} b_{t+1} \right)^{1-\alpha} = B_{t+1} \left(\frac{\beta_t}{B_t} b_{t+1} \right)^{1-\alpha}$$

and analogously for the green capital stock. Hence, with $A_B = \left(\frac{\beta_t}{B_t} \right)^{1-\alpha}$ and $A_G = \left(\frac{\gamma_t}{G_t} \right)^{1-\alpha}$, the representative agent's production at time t is:

$$P_t = A_B \cdot B_t \cdot b_t^{1-\alpha} + A_G \cdot G_t \cdot g_t^{1-\alpha}. \quad (9)$$

While for a single capital stock, this reduces to an AK -production function, here, the two production processes have capital-specific factors A_B and A_G and labour has to be allocated optimally. Assuming that labour can be allocated without further constraints, its optimal allocation in each time step only depends on the given capital stocks and technical progress values at that moment and leads to (see Appendix A.1)

$$g_t = b_t \left(\frac{A_G G_t}{A_B B_t} \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}, \quad (10)$$

where $L_t = 1$ for simplicity.

Considering an agent that starts with only a brown capital stock, the two options of continuing to invest only in the brown technology or starting to invest also in the green technology differ as follows. Sticking to just the brown sector, the agent's optimal

investment at t is

$$I = \frac{1}{1 + \rho} (\rho P_t - (1 - \delta)B_t) = \frac{1}{1 + \rho} (\rho A_B - 1 + \delta)B_t$$

and the respective utility will be

$$\ln(A_B B_t - I) + \rho \ln(A_B((1 - \delta)B_t + I)).$$

Comparing this with the case where the agent decides to begin investing in the green capital stock confirms the intuition that it is never optimal to start investing in a less productive capital stock based on the myopic optimization given in this setting (see Appendix A.1). That is, the given problem formulation is not suitable for studying transition possibilities from a brown to a green economy if the green technology is initially less productive. To nevertheless investigate mechanisms that might allow for transitions, below, we will present an agent-based model with agents that decide to switch to investing in the green technology for reasons external to the maximisation problem in Section 2. Even then, however, it is not sufficient that they myopically optimize, as shall be briefly laid out next.

3.2 Many standard agents

Considering an economy of n agents, in an endogenous technical progress setting it is usually assumed that the single agent ignores its contribution to technical progress. The resulting externality leads to a suboptimal growth path in models with a single capital stock.

To investigate the above-described setting with two capital stocks, here we also assume that agents do not consider their contribution to technical progress; they are "ignorant" agents in the sense of [Figueroa Alvarez and Wolf \(2024b\)](#), i.e., they consider the optimization problem set out in (1) - (7) without taking into account (8). If such agents have decided to hold both types of capital (for reasons external to their utility maximisation), the above-described maximisation problem leads to further difficulties.

As before, we assume that agents can optimally allocate their labour $L_t^{(i)} = 1$ to the two production processes in each time step and may use this knowledge for the investment decision. That is, agents will choose

$$g_t^{(i)} = \frac{G_t^{(i)}}{B_t^{(i)}} \left(\frac{\gamma_t}{\beta_t} \right)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} b_t^{(i)} \quad (11)$$

in each time step, see Appendix A.2. Then, their production at t is

$$\begin{aligned} P_t^{(i)} &= \left(B_t^{(i)} \right)^\alpha \left(\beta_t b_t^{(i)} \right)^{1-\alpha} + \left(G_t^{(i)} \right)^\alpha \left(\gamma_t \frac{G_t^{(i)}}{B_t^{(i)}} \left(\frac{\gamma_t}{\beta_t} \right)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} b_t^{(i)} \right)^{1-\alpha} \\ &= \left(B_t^{(i)} \right)^\alpha \left(\beta_t b_t^{(i)} \right)^{1-\alpha} \left(1 + \tau_t \frac{G_t^{(i)}}{B_t^{(i)}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where we set $\tau_t = \left(\frac{\gamma_t}{\beta_t}\right)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}}$ for notational simplicity. Taking this into account in the maximisation problem from Section 2, the solutions are (Appendix A.2):

$$I_G^{(i)} = \frac{\rho(\tau_{t+1} - \alpha) \left(P_t^{(i)} + (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)} \right) + (1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} (1 - \tau_{t+1} + \rho\tau_{t+1} - \rho\alpha\tau_{t+1})}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \quad (13)$$

$$I_B^{(i)} = \frac{\rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1) \left(P_t^{(i)} + (1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} \right) + (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)} (1 - \tau_{t+1} - \rho\tau_{t+1} + \rho\alpha)}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \quad (14)$$

While these results are not exactly illuminating, they show a few important issues: first, the value of τ_{t+1} depends on the investment decisions taken by all agents in step t . To determine their investments into green and brown capitals, agents would therefore need expectations on how the ratio between the technical progress values evolves.

Second, the investment values are undefined for $\tau_{t+1} = 1$ as a division by zero would happen. This is illustrated in Figure 1a. Recalling the definition of τ as a shortcut for the technical progress ratio with an exponent, this means that equal values for γ_{t+1} and β_{t+1} are not allowed to occur. Intuitively it seems to make sense that farms would not know which technology to invest in if both are equally productive. Starting in a situation where $\beta_0 \gg \gamma_0$, the value of τ_t will be very small initially. If a transition is to occur, however, one should expect this ratio to increase and eventually pass beyond 1, when the green technology becomes more productive than the brown one.

Figure 1b illustrates the optimal investments in terms of the given brown and green capital, further showing that it would not make sense for agents to hold both capital stocks and that optimal investments would be negative for most combinations of existing capital stocks.

4 Potential driving mechanisms behind green investment

Having seen that in the setting from Section 2, agents lack the incentive to start investing in green capital or to hold two capital stocks if they start nevertheless, one needs to consider driving mechanisms outside of the short-sighted utility maximisation paradigm to investigate transitions in the context of green growth, which are longer-term phenomena.

Hence, we present possible driving mechanisms that could facilitate this shift at the agent level, for incorporation into an agent-based model in the following section. These mechanisms aim to reconcile the agent's analytic, short-term behaviour with a longer-term component that we label "environmental concern". Environmental concern refers to an attitude towards environmental issues (see Hansla et al, 2008, and references therein).

According to Fransson and Gärling (1999), attitudes are shaped by beliefs and lead to intentions which are a proximal cause of behaviour, where behaviour is the actual

(a) Optimal investments against the future technical progress ratio

(b) Optimal investment surfaces in terms of the capitals holding

Fig. 1: Optimal green and brown investments, when $\gamma_t = 2.27$ and $\beta_t = 10.0$, $g_t = 0.4$ and $b_t = 0.6$, in terms of the: (1a) future technical progress ratio $\tau_{t+1} = \frac{\gamma_{t+1}}{\beta_{t+1}}$, when capital stocks are $B_t^{(i)} = G_t^{(i)} = 0.03$, and (1b) in terms of the farm's capital holdings (beige surface indicates when both investments are zero) when $\frac{\gamma_{t+1}}{\beta_{t+1}} = 0.3$.

action of an individual. In our model's context, the farms' beliefs could be of the idealistic type, e.g. 'I care about the environment', but the more useful interpretation seems to be a longer-term awareness that green transitions will be necessary after all. This could also be influenced by a farm's belief that 'the government is going to start to heavily tax brown production' or similar. These beliefs, or the corresponding attitude of environmental concern, then in a sense override the myopic decision to not invest in the less established but more environmental friendly technology. In the model, we do not make explicit the chain of components from beliefs via attitudes to intentions and action, but simply endow each farm with a binary belief: they care about the environment (represented by 1) or do not (represented by 0). This belief is then going to define the farm's investment behaviour and hence its capital holdings.

To update the agents' beliefs we use social integration strategies (Galesic et al, 2023). This umbrella term defines cognitive and social algorithms –such as opinion dynamics models– designed to integrate information about beliefs, behaviours, and intentions within social environments. In particular, we consider two commonly used types of belief dynamics: the voter model and the majority rule (Castellano et al, 2009).

4.1 The Voter Model

In general, the voter model is an *averaging social integration strategy*, that is, agents form a weighted average of their personal beliefs and those of their neighbours about an issue (Galesic et al, 2021). Here, as we consider binary beliefs, an even simpler imitation process will be considered. The voter model is well studied (Redner, 2019; Castellano et al, 2009) and presents the simplest form of opinion dynamics, which

is why we consider it a suitable test case for modelling a socially influenced driving mechanism for a green transition.

In the agent-based model, we endow each farm with a binary belief/opinion $\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} \in \{0, 1\}$, i.e. at time t , the farm either cares ($\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = 1$) or does not care ($\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = 0$) about the environment, where the latter is the default. The farm’s belief can change by interaction with a neighbouring agent who has a different belief, however, we consider agents that do care stubborn, that is, they will not revert to $\mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} = 0$. We can describe the opinion dynamics as follows

$$\mathcal{O}_{t+1}^{(i)} = \begin{cases} \mathcal{O}_t^{(j)} & \text{if } \mathcal{O}_t^{(j)} = 1 \text{ where } j \in n_i \\ \mathcal{O}_t^{(i)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where, at each time step t , a random agent i is drawn and randomly chooses an agent j from its neighbourhood n_i .

When the farm’s belief changes, she starts to care for the environment. Therefore her environmental attitude is modified and consequently her investment behaviour changes, i.e. she is going to start investing in green capital.

4.2 The Majority Rule

The majority rule is a *frequency-dependent* social integration strategy. These types of strategies favour beliefs that surpass a specific threshold of the proportion of one’s social contacts on an issue (Galesic et al, 2021). The majority rule is the most well-known strategy in this category. This rule reflects when a public debate about an issue is happening. We can assume that individuals meet at random in a space shaped by their social life (Galambos, 2002). At each time step t , when a group of r random agents meet and discuss the issue, the individuals update their beliefs to match the beliefs of the majority (Castellano et al, 2009). For our set-up, green agents are stubborn, therefore if the majority’s belief is $\mathcal{O}_t = 0$, all the discussion group’s farms keep their previous belief.

For a group $G_r = \{1, \dots, r\}$, of r random agents, we define the group’s average belief at time t ,

$$\hat{\mathcal{O}}_t = \frac{1}{r} \sum_{j \in G_r} \mathcal{O}_t^{(j)}.$$

So at each time step t , for every farm in the discussion group, the beliefs are updated as follows:

$$\mathcal{O}_{t+1}^{(k)} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{when } \hat{\mathcal{O}}_t > 1/2 \\ \mathcal{O}_t^{(k)} & \text{when } \hat{\mathcal{O}}_t \leq 1/2 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

5 The agent-based model

The agent-based model developed for this work is based on the Agent-based Ramsey growth model with endogenous technical progress (ABRam-T, for the code and ODD-protocol see (Figueroa Alvarez et al, 2024)). Adding the distinction of capital into “brown” and “green”, the corresponding model hence becomes the Agent-based

Ramsey growth model with Brown and Green capital (ABRam-BG, for the code and ODD protocol see [Figueroa Alvarez and Wolf \(2024a\)](#)).

The basic features and functioning of agents have been described above: agents hold one or two capital stocks from which they produce with the help of their available labour, where $L_t^{(i)} = 1$ is assumed for all agents and all time steps for simplicity. Technical progress for the two production processes evolves with the total capital stocks. Agents gain utility from consumption and take part in an opinion dynamics process, described in the previous section.

Apart from the rather straightforward labour allocation decision, the main decision variable of agents is their investment. In this model, the agents' investment strategies depend on their capital holding. If the agents only hold green or brown capital, they invest according to the optimization of (1) given the constraints (2)–(7), ignoring (8) (hence called ignorant agents by [Figueroa Alvarez and Wolf, 2024b](#)), i.e.

$$I_t^{\text{Ig}^{(i)}} = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha\rho} \left(\rho\alpha \left(K_t^{(i)} \right)^\alpha \eta_t^{1-\alpha} - (1 - \delta)K_t^{(i)} \right) = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha\rho} \left(\rho\alpha P_t^{(i)} - (1 - \delta)K_t^{(i)} \right),$$

where $K_t^{(i)}$ is either the agent's brown ($B_t^{(i)}$) or green ($G_t^{(i)}$) capital. At initialization, agents that hold brown capital are of opinion 0, and agents that hold green capital have opinion 1.

Through the opinion dynamics process, farms that hold only brown capital may change their opinion and hence begin to invest in green capital. As described above, at this point, the short-sighted utility maximisation no longer makes sense, for the problems laid out in Section 3.2. We hence consider agents that quite radically decide to go into green investment: agents with brown capital that change their opinion to 1 will not invest in brown capital any more. They still use their brown capital for production, but run it down by depreciation step by step. In the production step, they still optimise labour allocation to the two production processes as given in (11). However, in their investment decision, they balance consumption and green investment only, leading to

$$I_G^{(i)} = \frac{1}{1 + \alpha\rho} \left(\rho\alpha P_t^{(i)} - (1 - \delta)(B_t^{(i)} + G_t^{(i)}) \right),$$

which corresponds to the ignorant agent's investment above, with the only difference being that the capital stock has two components which are also both active in production.

Farms that invest in green capital will be referred to as “green farms” later, independently of whether they were initially brown farms and hence own both capital stocks or were initially green farms that only own green capital. Note that while initially, all brown farms are identical, as are all green farms, the random switching of agents from brown to green provides heterogeneity between farms. Depending on the time of the switch, farms have accumulated different amounts of brown capital once they begin investing in green, and hence also the amounts invested will generally differ.

Apart from the farms, the model contains a statistician agent who collects information, computes relevant aggregate variables (such as the levels of technical progress) and communicates information back to the farms.

5.1 Sequence of events

The model evolution, illustrated in Figure 2, takes place via the following updates in each time step of the simulation.

Fig. 2: Flow diagram of the model

1. The time index is increased by one, so $B_{t+1}^{(i)}$ and $G_{t+1}^{(i)}$ computed in the previous time step becomes $B_t^{(i)}$ and $G_t^{(i)}$ respectively.
2. The statistician aggregates the system's capitals by summing over all agents, i.e., $B_t = \sum_i B_t^{(i)}$ and $G_t = \sum_i G_t^{(i)}$.
3. From B_t and G_t the statistician computes the productivities β_t and γ_t , using Equation (8).
4. All farms receive information about the current green and brown productivity levels.
5. Farms decide how to allocate their labour depending on their capital holding. If they own one type of capital they allocate all their labour into that capital, otherwise they allocate their labour using (11).
6. All farms produce according to Equation (2)
7. Farms compute the optimal investment $I_t^{(i)}$ according to their beliefs and capital holding.
8. Each farm computes its instantaneous utility $u(C_t^{(i)})$ and adds it to the previous cumulative utility to obtain the current one, $U_t^{(i)}$.
9. Depending on the social integration strategy chosen, one farm is randomly selected, and interacts with a random neighbour according to (15) or a group of agents is randomly drawn and interacts according to (16).
10. The farms update their opinion.

11. The statistician computes the GDP and growth rate of the system. Since the economy is closed, the GDP is the sum of all the farms' output

$$GDP_t = \sum_i P_t^{(i)}. \quad (17)$$

And the *growth rate* g_t of the economy is given by

$$g_t = \frac{GDP_t - GDP_{t-1}}{GDP_{t-1}}. \quad (18)$$

12. Farms update their capital, using Equations (5) and (6) to compute $G_{t+1}^{(i)}$ and $B_{t+1}^{(i)}$.

6 Results and Discussion

To investigate the potential of green transitions in the given model, we define a **green transition** along the lines of Lamperti et al (2020): the economy's green output reaches a share of 85% of the total output and does not fall back again. After introducing the general set-up for simulations in Section 6.1, Section 6.2 shows that for the opinion dynamics mechanisms described, green transitions are the exception rather than the rule. Section 6.3 explores the effects of varying the numbers of interacting agents on the probability of green transitions, before Section 6.4 considers the economic dynamics arising in various (non-)transition scenarios.

6.1 The simulation setting

For the experiments, we consider an agent-based economy of 100 farms where 80 farms initially hold only brown capital and the other 20 farms hold only green capital; this initial ratio is based on Shayegh et al (2023), who report that the current share of green goods in total consumption is about 20%. Since the model does not distinguish between brown and green consumption, as an approximation, we translate this ratio to the farms' capital holding and the economy's initial technical progress levels. The model's and agents' parameters used are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters for the ABM simulations

Parameter	Name	Value
n	Number of farms	100
t	Length of the simulation in time steps	120
α	Output elasticity of capital	0.33
δ	Capital depreciation rate	0.05
ρ	Factor to discount future felicity	0.99
$B_0^{(i)}$	Brown farms' initial capital	0.1
$G_0^{(i)}$	Green farms' initial capital	0.1
β_0	Initial brown technological progress	7.72
γ_0	Initial green technological progress	1.54

While these parameters are partially chosen according to conventional values occurring in economic works, they are not calibrated to represent any specific national or regional economy nor a specific time frame.² Thus, the economic system under consideration remains abstract and results are not to be interpreted quantitatively but only qualitatively.

Running the model with these parameters without any interaction between the agents produces a **baseline scenario**. In this case, each farm sticks to its initial capital stock and the economy grows deterministically. In particular, the brown capital stock grows very quickly, so we limit the number of time steps for simulations to 120 to avoid numerical problems. The number of runs, on the other hand, is set to 350 in all steps of analysis; on the choice of this number see Appendix B. As a first step, we investigate green transitions under the social integration strategies as presented in Sections 4.1 and 4.2 with the further parameters from Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters for the standard social integration strategies

Parameter	Name	Value
\mathcal{N}	network for voter dynamics	Small-world
$f^{(i)}$	number of friends of farm i in voter dynamics	5
r	number of random agents that meet under the majority rule	5

6.2 Standard driving mechanisms

6.2.1 The underlying opinion dynamics

As the opinion dynamics in the present ABM work as a driver but are not themselves influenced by the economic dynamics, it makes sense to first look into this independent process. Due to the simplicity of the mechanisms chosen, these underlying processes are well known. As the state space of the opinion dynamics, consider the number of green farms, i.e., $x \in \mathcal{X} = \{20, \dots, 100\}$ for the setting specified above. We denote by X_t the (random) number of green farms at time t , with $X_0 = 20$ by assumption. As farms can only switch from brown to green, but cannot switch back, the number of green farms can only increase (or stay the same) throughout a simulation.

For the voter model defined above, at each time step the interaction may lead to one or no farm switching. The probability of a switch is that of drawing a brown farm and then a green farm that it imitates, while no switch occurs if a green farm is drawn first, or a brown farm draws another brown farm to interact with. The corresponding probabilities depend on the number of green and brown farms in the system at the time of the interaction. As a benchmark case³, consider a fully connected network,

²In fact, this would hardly be possible in the setting chosen: due to the myopic decision-making of farms, to produce positive investment, the technical progress values are chosen in such a way that they produce very high growth rates as compared with real-world data (see also [Figueroa Alvarez and Wolf, 2024b](#)).

³The following theoretical considerations do not immediately translate to the agent-based model, in that for the voter dynamics the network used is a small-world network where each agent has 5 friends, rather than a fully connected one.

i.e., each farm can interact with all other farms. Then⁴,

$$P(X_{t+1} = x + 1 | X_t = x) = \frac{100 - x}{100} \cdot \frac{x}{99}$$

$$P(X_{t+1} = x | X_t = x) = 1 - \frac{100 - x}{100} \cdot \frac{x}{99}$$

$$P(X_{t+1} = y | X_t = x) = 0 \text{ for any other } y.$$

Figure 3a illustrates the probabilities for moving from x to $x + 1$ green farms (green solid line) and for staying at x green farms (green dashed line) for all possible values of x . The highest probability of a switch in this setting occurs at about 50% of green farms where the probability is close to 1/4. With a fully connected network, each farm has a positive probability of switching, so that in the long run, all farms will be green.⁵ However, when starting with 20 green farms, this will on average take around 650-time steps (see Appendix A.3), which is far beyond the 120 steps considered here. Figure 3b illustrates the average waiting times for reaching each possible number of green farms when starting at 20 green agents (green line).

Fig. 3: Comparison of switching probabilities (3a) and average waiting times (3b) for the Voter model (green) and the Majority rule (red, blue, purple).

For the majority rule with group size $r = 5$, none, one or two agents may switch to green at each time step. Here, no underlying network structure is specified, so that all farms can interact with all others. The corresponding probabilities are shown in Figure 3a, where the blue line represents the probability of 2 agents switching, the red one that of 1 agent, and the purple line sums these two into the probability of any switch occurring, while the purple dashed line presents the complementary probability of staying at the same number of green agents. The expected waiting times for reaching each possible number of green farms are again illustrated in Figure 3b (purple line,

⁴Note that the first term in the probability computation, the probability of drawing a brown farm, remains the same for any network structure. However, the probability that this farm then draws a green farm to imitate depends on this particular farm's group of neighbours in the network.

⁵If the network structure contains clusters of brown farms that cannot interact with any green farms, these agents will never switch.

again, see Appendix A.3), where it can be seen that with the 1-step voter dynamics, 21-37 green agents are reached faster, whereas the majority rule is quicker to reach any number of green agents from 38 to 100. In particular, the expected time for reaching an economy in which all farms are green is only about 1/3 of that for the voter model.

6.2.2 The resulting transition dynamics

With the green transition definition given above and the time frame of 120 steps, there is a marked difference in transition dynamics between the two social integration strategies, see Figure 4. For the Voter model simulations (4a), the green output share initially declines from the starting value of 8.0% to below 1% and does not recover in the given time frame. This pattern can be considered a *carbon lock-in* similar to the definition by Lamperti et al (2020) – a share of green output dropping below 15% and not rising above this value again. In contrast, the Majority rule for a group size $r = 5$ as driving mechanism for a green transition seems more effective, since out of 350 simulations 35.14% reach the 85% threshold of green output by time step 110, and never fall back (Figure 4c).

Fig. 4: Evolution of the green output share and number of green farms (note the different scales) for 30 simulations for the two standard social integration strategies.

This difference can be explained by the difference in number of green farms resulting from the two different mechanisms seen in Figures 4b and 4d. Apparently, in the

Voter model, the belief dynamics are too slow to lead to a green transition, while the more rapid evolution of the number of green agents in about a third of the simulations under the majority rule drives a green transition. Note that for the Voter model, only one simulation reaches the theoretically expected number of green agents by 120-time steps, namely around 50 agents (Figure 4b). Most simulations remain much lower, indicating that the structure of the network slows down the opinion dynamics process as compared to the benchmark case with a fully connected network. The figures for the Majority rule show that one cannot characterise the picture through a simple statement like "a green transition happens if x agents are green"; a feature that is also confirmed by Figure 5 which indicates that the number of green agents at the point where the transition occurs lies scattered in a range of values for both opinion mechanisms.

Fig. 5: Scatter plots of the number of green agents and first-time step when the green share output is bigger than 0.85 for (5a) the voter dynamics when 4 agents interact per time step and (5b) the standard majority rule.

Whether and when a transition happens also depends on the speed and the timing of the opinion dynamics process in relation to the economic process, as the brown capital grows alongside the opinion dynamics process happening, and does so initially faster than the green capital. Hence, we need a measure that quantifies the rate of change of the number of green farms throughout a simulation and needs to investigate how this interacts with the economic processes.

6.3 Exploration of the number of interacting agents

Having seen that the opinion dynamics under the given Voter model is too slow to lead to green transitions, we consider a slight modification of the model, where the opinion dynamics step is iterated several times in each (economic) time step. These iterations are independent of each other (in the sense of probability theory) so this corresponds to a re-scaling of time of the opinion dynamics with respect to the economic dynamics.

Also under the Majority rule, most simulations (about 65%) do not show a green transition. Here, we vary the number of interacting agents, meaning that we investigate various group size parameters r , see Table 2.

Figure 6 provides average numbers of green agents over time in simulations for both belief dynamics for the different numbers of interacting agents, where 6a displays the re-scaling of time with the Voter model: the more agents interact, the less time is needed for all farms to switch to green, a state that will be referred to as **consensus** in the following.

Fig. 6: Average numbers of green agents across 350 simulations when varying the number of interacting agents. The black dashed lines correspond to the standard cases considered above.

As can be seen in Figure 6b, the pattern for the majority rule with different group sizes is less straightforward. Obviously, for group sizes of 41 and larger, no brown farm can ever switch to green because, with 20 green farms in the beginning, no majority of more than 20 agents can be reached. The time to reach a consensus further depends on whether the group size is even or odd. This follows from the definition which requires a strict green majority to convince the minority, which is not the case if a draw occurs (Appendix A.3). To capture the speed of the opinion dynamics process, i.e., how fast the number of green farms is changing throughout a simulation, we define the **consensus rate**⁶ as

$$\text{Consensus rate} = \frac{X_t - X_{t-1}}{X_{t-1}} \times 100\%, \quad (19)$$

⁶In fact, this is the growth rate of the number of green farms at each time step, however, since it depends only on the opinion dynamics process, and in order not to confuse it with growth rates in the economic sense, e.g., of these farms' capital stocks, we refer to it as consensus rate. As is usual for growth rates, the denominator scales the change measured at each step to the number of green agents present at that moment, so that the switch of the first brown agent to green is weighted larger than a one-agent-change when almost all agents are green. Also, this definition implies that the mean consensus rate of a sequence of small changes is smaller than that of a sequence where the same total amount of green farms is obtained by a single large jump. In previous work about convergence speed in opinion dynamics models, the focus is usually on bounds for the number of time steps needed to reach consensus, and results for models with general (not fully connected) networks and asynchronous updating (one agent per step interacts with others) are rare (Berenbrink et al, 2024). Further research should specify a more precise measure for capturing the speed of the opinion dynamics process that is better adapted to the influence it has on the economic dynamics. However, in the computational exploration to follow, we will use this growth rate as an approximate measure of the speed of the opinion dynamics process throughout a simulation.

where X_t and X_{t-1} are the random number of green farms at time steps t and $t - 1$, and the mean consensus rate is the average of these values over the 120-time steps of a simulation.

For the Voter model, it is evident that increasing the number of pairwise interactions per time step increases the mean consensus rate, and it is one of the factors that influence when a green transition is reached (see Figure 7a). In contrast, for the Majority rule, average transition times are beyond 120 time steps with all parameters r . Groups of size 5, 7 and 9 agents exhibit the highest consensus rates (see Figure 7b; it was already seen in Figure 6b that these are the group sizes with the largest number of green agents). For bigger discussion groups, especially with a group size larger than 20, consensus rates are very low and decreasing.

Fig. 7: Averages across 350 simulations for mean consensus rates and transition times, for different numbers of interacting agents.

Table 3 reports the likelihood of a green transition to occur across different selected numbers of interacting agents. For the Voter dynamics, we observe the expected: the likelihood of a green transition increases when the number of interacting agents increases. For the Majority rule dynamics, the highest green transition probabilities, occurring for group sizes $r = 5, 7$ and 9 never exceed 60%.

Returning to Figure 7, we see that for a transition to be reached in the time frame of interest, the mean consensus rate has to exceed a threshold of about 1.1, which on average is not the case for the Majority rule. However, when looking at single simulation runs under both social integration strategies, we observe that those simulations which exceed a consensus rate of 1 reach a green transition (see all plots in Figure 8). Yet, simulations with the same consensus rate may show different transition times (for instance see Figures 8a, 8b, 8f, or 8g).

Figure 8 also displays the relationship between the average brown capital growth rate and the transition time, indicating that lower brown capital growth rates come with early green transitions. The growth rate of the brown capital stock can be seen as an indicator of the timing of farms switching to green: the earlier farms switch away from brown investment, the more slowly the brown capital stock in the system grows as fewer farms invest in it.

Figure 9 presents a clear trend of decreasing brown capital growth rates and transition times with increasing consensus rates. Together, these results confirm that it is

Table 3: Likelihood of green transition for the social integration strategies across 350 simulations when varying the number of interacting agents.

Social integration strategy	No. of interacting agents	Transition to green likelihood		Carbon lock-in likelihood		
		At time step 110	At time step 120	At time step 110	At time step 120	
Voter dynamics	1	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	
	2	0.29	1.43	94.00	89.14	
	3	31.71	51.14	31.14	17.43	
	4	87.71	95.43	1.71	0.86	
	5	99.43	100.00	0.00	0.00	
	6	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	
	10	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	
	100	100.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	
	Majority rule	3	0.00	0.00	100.00	98.57
		4	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00
5		35.14	46.29	49.43	39.14	
6		0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	
7		50.57	59.14	41.71	30.57	
9		44.00	55.43	46.29	37.71	
20		1.14	1.43	98.86	98.00	
37		0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	
39		0.29	0.29	99.71	99.71	
40		0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	
100	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00		

Voter Dynamics

Majority rule

Fig. 8: Mean consensus rate against mean brown capital growth rate for the Voter dynamics with $j = 2, 3, 4, 100$ interacting agents (8a – 8d) and under the Majority rule group sizes of $r = 7, 15, 20, 41$ agents (8e – 8h).

an interplay between the speed and the timing of the opinion dynamics process that creates green transitions. Comparing selected simulations that have the same consen-

Fig. 9: Average consensus rate against brown capital growth rates across simulations for different numbers of interacting agents

sus rates, Figure 10 illustrates how different transition times can come about through differences in the timing of farms changing their belief and beginning to invest in green capital.

In summary, we find that repeated pairwise interactions are more efficient than single interactions of larger groups of agents and that the interplay between timing

Fig. 10: Evolution of the number of green farms and green output share at mean consensus rates 1.002 (purple lines) and 1.311 (blue lines) for the Voter model (dashed line) and Majority rule (solid line).

and speed of farms changing to green investment is quite involved. Hence, even though the economic dynamics is deterministic and the only source of stochasticity lies in the opinion dynamics process, it is not completely straightforward to characterise which simulations lead to green transitions and when. We leave a suitably aggregated mathematical model, that could help do this, to future work. Here, instead, we will make use of the explicit micro-level representation in the computational ABM to further investigate the economic dynamics of the system in terms of their consequences for the single agents.

6.4 Economic dynamics

To better understand economic consequences of green transitions, in this section, we explore the economic landscape of three simulations from Figure 10. We use them as representative cases of three scenarios we are interested in asses: carbon lock-in, early and late transition. Table 4 presents a description of these scenarios.

Table 4: Scenarios with their respective social integration strategies, average consensus rate and growth rate of brown capital

Scenario	Social Integration strategy	No. of interacting agents per time step	Average Consensus rate	Brown capital growth rate
Early transition	Voter Dynamics	5	1.311	2.21
Late transition	Voter Dynamics	2	1.002	2.98
Carbon lock-in	Majority Rule	15	1.002	3.56
Baseline	-	0	0.000	3.76

6.4.1 Macro-level indicators

In particular, we use two dimensions for evaluating these scenarios: the economic dimension, which includes the evolution of the capital stocks and the economy’s GDP, and the environmental dimension via the economy’s CO₂ emissions.⁷

Recall the baseline scenario, in which all farms stick to investing in their initial capital stock and no switching of brown to green farms takes place. In comparison with this case, the economy’s green capital increases and there is a reduction of brown capital (Figure 11) in all scenarios with opinion dynamics taking place. For the early transition scenario, we observe a more dramatic decrease in brown capital in comparison to the other two.

Fig. 11: Evolution of the economy’s capital stocks for the baseline scenario (brown solid line), early transition scenario (dashed line), late transition scenario (dashed line with dots) and carbon lock-in scenario (dash-dotted line with stars).

Unexpectedly, the carbon lock-in scenario exhibits the highest levels of green capital among all the scenarios. As even a single farm switches to green, the build-up of brown capital that has happened up to this point produces a green investment amount that makes the scenario surpass the green capital level of the other cases. The size of the green capital stock is hence not an indicator of green transitions.

Figure 12a shows that GDP is lower in scenarios with switches to green capital than in the baseline case. However, all three scenarios still exhibit growth and the late transition leads to the worst outcome in terms of loss of GDP, while the early transition scenario has lower GDP in the beginning but catches up eventually and surpasses the late transition scenario in the long run. In terms of CO₂ emissions, the early transition provides a marked decrease in emissions compared to the other scenarios (see Figure 12b). Of course, these results are limited by the very stylized model used that does not take into account climate shocks, environmental degradation, etc. We leave questions around how these would affect the results to further work.

⁷For information on accounting of the CO₂ emissions, see Appendix C.

Fig. 12: GDP (12a) and CO₂ emissions (12b) for the baseline scenario (brown solid line), early transition scenario (blue dashed line), late transition scenario (red dashed line with dots) and carbon lock-in scenario (orange dash-dotted line with stars).

6.4.2 New green farms

As a last element of our analysis, we explore the economic consequences from changing opinion, and hence investment behaviour, at the individual level. In the early transition and the carbon lock-in scenario, we investigate two types of new green farms: early and late adopters, which are, respectively, the first farms to change opinion in each simulation and the last ones before time step 110⁸. Table 5 shows the timing of the opinion changes. To compare these agents' economic outcomes with those of agents that stick to their initial opinion, we call the latter "stubborn"; stubborn green farms are initialized holding green capital, and stubborn brown farms stick with investing in brown capital over the whole simulation. As previously done, we also compare these agents with green and brown farms from the baseline scenario to understand any differences from the baseline case. In both scenarios, we find clear differences between the

Table 5: Transition time for the early transition and carbon lock-in scenario and times when the early and late adopter change opinion.

	Early Transition	Carbon lock-in
Transition time (time step)	72	> 120
Early adopter	1	66
Late adopter	106	94

farms' capital stock evolution throughout the simulation (Figure 13). While almost all the farms' capital stocks exhibit growth, in the early transition scenario, the stubborn brown farm's capital stock stagnates. In comparison with the green baseline farm, stubborn green farms benefit greatly from directed technical progress, which increases with every new green farm adding to it. This can be seen more obviously in the carbon lock-in scenario where shortly after the early adopter switches to green investment,

⁸This threshold is chosen 10 steps before the end of the simulation so that consequences from the switch can be observed.

it experiences a quick increase in its capital stock to the level of this early adopter, which in turn departs downwards from the baseline brown farm’s capital trajectory.

Fig. 13: Agents’ total capital stock in the early transition and the carbon lock-in scenario.)

To further scrutinize this effect, Figure 14 shows the evolution of the capital stock growth rates of the observed farms through the simulations, where the spikes correspond to sudden increases in the farms’ capital stock.

Fig. 14: Agents’ capital growth rates in the early transition and the carbon lock-in scenario.

When a farm with low levels of capital (such as a late adopter in the transition scenario or the stubborn green farm in the carbon lock-in scenario) experiences high levels of technical progress – be this due to its own switch to the by then more productive green capital or due to another farm with comparatively high investment due to a large previous build-up of capital moving to green – its production increases. This, in turn, augments the farms’ investment, causing a rise in its capital stock. The magnitude of these spikes is related to how unproductive the farm’s capital is compared to the other existing capital. This is confirmed by a detailed examination of the beginning of the early transition scenario (Figure 14a). Here, we see a small increase in the stubborn green farm’s growth rate as the first brown farm begins investing in green, followed by a second increase when a new farm begins investing in green. These increases become smaller as the productivity ratio between brown and green capital

approaches 1, and the largest spikes are those of the late adopter in the transition or the first adopter in the carbon lock-in scenario. Here, the different productivities have led to one of the capital stocks building up much faster than the other one, so that the investment of a new green farms causes a big jump in productivity. This explains why farms that own unproductive capital are highly ‘sensitive’ to new technological progress levels when either these farms adopt more productive capital – as is the case of late adopter in the early transition scenario – or when other farms adopt their capital – as is the case of the stubborn green farm in the carbon lock-in scenario.

Fig. 15: Farms capital growth rate in the early transition scenario

Indeed, the current technological ratio $\frac{\gamma_t}{\beta_t}$ plays a major role in the responsiveness of the farms to changes in their capital growth rates. Naturally, the brown farms’ capital growth rates decrease as farms stop investing in brown capital. With more farms investing in green capital, the technological ratio increases. When $\frac{\gamma_t}{\beta_t} < 1$, the stubborn green farms – that during this period hold the less productive capital – exhibit sudden increases and decreases (since not in every time step other farms turn green). Meanwhile, new green farms that adopt early experience a decrease in their capital growth rates, since they are investing in a less productive capital. Before catching up with the growth trend of the stubborn green farm, the farms experience a period of lower growth, the length of this period is inversely proportional to how big the ratio between technologies is, i.e., the smaller the ratio, the longer the period of lower growth. On the other hand, when $\frac{\gamma_t}{\beta_t} > 1$, the new green farms are the ones that exhibit spikes due to the decreasing productivity of brown capital. During this period, the stubborn green farms’ capital growth rates increase since the green technology is more productive than the brown technology.

It is worth noting that there is a small time window from when the technological ratio is one to when the green output share is more than 85% where the new green farms experience a sudden increase in their growth rates and they immediately reach the green farms’ growth trend. These “lucky” farms, at the end of the simulation, have higher levels of cumulative utility compared to the rest of the farms in the early transition scenario (Figure 16c).

Fig. 16: Early transition scenario farms' cumulative utility

Further analysis of the cumulative utility of new green farms reveals that the farms in the carbon lock-in scenario exhibit higher levels of utility at the end of the simulations compared to farms in the early transition scenario (Figure 17 and Table 6). This means that we do not find green growth in the sense of at the same time decreasing emissions and increasing overall utility in this model. However, given its very stylized nature, the farms' utility does not take into account the economy's environmental quality, which could decrease given the higher CO₂ emission that this scenario exhibits (Figure 12b). Further research should address how these could affect the results. However, the results also suggest that agents who change attitude towards green investment, in both scenarios, have a positive outcome in terms of capital and utility compared to the baseline scenario. And the stubborn-brown agents, in a successful transition scenario, would struggle, given that the brown capital declines slowly, which decreases the agent's utility.

Fig. 17: Carbon lock-in scenario farms' cumulative utility

Farms	Early Transition Scenario	Carbon Lock-In
Baseline brown	11378.96	
Baseline green	4091.42	
Stubborn brown	9284.91	11268.58
Stubborn green	9933.65	4091.42
Early adopter	9956.72	10926.00
Lucky adopter	10136.18	-
Late adopter	9724.62	11157.87

Table 6: Farms' cumulative utility at time step 120

In summary, from an individual perspective, farms should try to switch during the "lucky" period. As this period depends on when other farms switch, this is of course impossible. From a macroeconomic perspective, the earlier a transition happens, the better in terms of both emissions and long-term growth. That is, if we consider a transition to a green economy necessary and hence exclude the baseline case as a possibility, a green growth story can be told: the earliest transition comes with both decreased emissions and increased welfare in comparison with later transitions. Given that the first movers pay in this setting, policy could compensate them for it,

reiterating the results by [Acemoglu et al \(2012\)](#), which finds that a subsidy for green production needs to be in place only for a certain amount of time.

7 Conclusions and Outlook

In this paper, we present an agent-based model built on the underlying mechanisms of directed technical progress and opinion dynamics to gain an understanding, at a theoretical and qualitative level, of the feasibility of green transitions. The theoretical background of the model is a Ramsey growth model. We start out considering agents that are myopic utility maximisers in a setting with endogenous technical progress and two capital stocks – green (low carbon intensity) and brown (high carbon intensity) – with their corresponding technical progress levels. This setting fails to provide a satisfactory response as to why agents would switch from a well-established technology to a less productive one. Also, we find that agents holding both capital stocks show optimal investments which are not continuous in the technical progress ratio between the two capital stocks, and for most combinations of capital stocks, the investments would be negative. This suggests including longer-term considerations when studying long-term economic phenomena, such as a green transition.

We do this by integrating beliefs and a social environment (a network) in the ABM, to reconcile the short-sightedness of agents with a longer-term economic phenomenon. This was done by endowing agents with a binary belief: they either care (we call these agents green agents) or not (brown agents) about the environment, therefore they believe (or not) in the necessity of a green transition. We also assume that green agents are stubborn. When an agent starts to care about the environment, she begins to invest in green capital. The agents' beliefs change stochastically, according to a Voter model or Majority rule dynamics, which are two of the most studied mechanisms in opinion dynamics.

When these belief dynamics interact with the corresponding economic landscape, we find that earlier green transitions decrease emissions and increase growth compared to later transitions, confirming the finding by [Lamperti et al \(2020\)](#), that a green transition needs to be a *timely event*. The interaction of opinion dynamics and economic dynamics can be statistically characterized by the speed of the opinion dynamics process (indicating how fast brown agents switch to green) and the growth of the brown capital stock (as an indicator of when agents start switching to green). While in this model, there is no feedback from the economic dynamics to the opinion dynamics process – to be included in future work, as such feedback may change the system's dynamics [Dávila-Fernández et al \(2024\)](#) – and hence, the economic dynamics is deterministic once the opinion changes have been randomly determined, the interactions are too intricate for a simple characterization at the level of the ABM. Future work should look into aggregating the model to make a mathematical analysis, that goes beyond statistics about a large number of runs, feasible.

The comparison of the two opinion dynamics processes considered shows that multiple pairwise interactions seem to be more effective than a collective interaction among more than two agents to drive a green transition. However, multiple Majority interactions within an economic time step have not been explored here. To enhance findings,

further research might explore the effects of the transition feasibility and economic dynamics for a multiple majority rule, i.e. several discussion groups happening at each time step.

Finally, at first sight, we recover the general result from much of standard economics that adopting green or sustainable technologies comes with a loss in GDP compared to a scenario where no such adoption occurs. If we start from the premise that business as usual (and hence our baseline scenario) is simply not an option, due to all kinds of planetary boundaries, we find that the earlier a green transition is reached, the lower the emissions and the higher the GDP that result. In this sense, at a very abstract and merely qualitative level, this work confirms the idea of green growth: lower emissions with higher prosperity.

Future work should incorporate into the model many further aspects that are missing from our analysis to improve the evaluation of our results, such as climate shocks, environmental degradation and feedback dynamics from the economy to the agents' beliefs as green agents that revert to brown production, different network topologies, and agents with different initial capital holdings, etc. The most urgent extension of the model seems to be the inclusion of a labour market, to investigate whether the proof-of-concept by [Steudle et al \(2018\)](#) can be transferred to actual paths towards green growth.

Appendix A Mathematical appendix

A.1 The representative agent's utility maximisation

As labour allocation only influences utility through the amount produced, one can instead consider the problem of allocating labour in such a way as to maximise production. To this end, let $g_t = L_t - b_t$ and set

$$\frac{dP_t}{db_t} = (1 - \alpha)A_B B_t b_t^{-\alpha} - (1 - \alpha)A_G G_t \cdot (L_t - b_t)^{-\alpha} = 0.$$

The result in (10) follows by solving and substituting g_t back for $L_t - b_t$. Alternatively solving completely for b_t ,

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - \alpha)A_B B_t b_t^{-\alpha} - (1 - \alpha)A_G G_t \cdot (L_t - b_t)^{-\alpha} &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow (A_B B_t)^{-\frac{1}{\alpha}} b_t &= (A_G G_t)^{-\frac{1}{\alpha}} (L_t - b_t) \\ \Rightarrow \left((A_G G_t)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} + (A_B B_t)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \right) b_t &= (A_B B_t)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} L_t \\ \Rightarrow b_t = \frac{(A_B B_t)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} L_t}{(A_G G_t)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} + (A_B B_t)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} &\text{ and consequently } g_t = \frac{(A_G G_t)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} L_t}{(A_G G_t)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} + (A_B B_t)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \end{aligned}$$

This could be substituted into Equations (4) and (7), to then optimize the investment decisions. However, with I_B and I_G terms in B_{t+1} and G_{t+1} respectively, and

hence also in b_{t+1} and g_{t+1} , the calculations become too involved to convey an understanding at first sight. We hence continue with a more intuitive comparison of the cases where the agent does or does not decide to start investing in green capital.

To compare the utility of only brown investment

$$\ln(A_B B_t - I) + \rho \ln(A_B((1 - \delta)B_t + I)). \quad (\text{A1})$$

in the case where the agent decides to begin investing in the green capital stock, consider first that the total amount invested remains the same. Then the utility gained from current consumption (the first term in (A1)) also remains the same, and we need to compare the utilities from future consumption, which equals future production. Note that we consider the case that not only $\beta_0 \gg \gamma_0$ but also $A_B \gg A_G$, as the conventional brown technology is the more productive one. Let I_G be the amount invested in the green technology, then P_{t+1} with green investment is

$$\begin{aligned} & A_B((1 - \delta)B_t + I - I_G)b_{t+1}^{1-\alpha} + A_G I_G g_{t+1}^{1-\alpha} \\ &= A_B((1 - \delta)B_t + I - I_G)b_{t+1}^{1-\alpha} + A_G I_G \left(b_{t+1} \left(\frac{A_G I_G}{A_B B_{t+1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \right)^{1-\alpha} \\ &< A_B((1 - \delta)B_t + I - I_G) + A_G I_G \left(\frac{A_G I_G}{A_B B_{t+1}} \right)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} \text{ as } b_{t+1} < 1 \\ &= A_B((1 - \delta)B_t + I) + I_G \left(-A_B + A_G \left(\frac{A_G I_G}{A_B B_{t+1}} \right)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

This is less than P_{t+1} with only brown capital (which is the first term in the sum) as the second term in the sum is negative, due to $A_G < A_B, I_G < B_{t+1}$ so that the fraction term is less than one.

As the utility maximisation balances investment and consumption at time t in an optimal way, to make up for this smaller production at $t + 1$, the investment would have to be increased, which however would decrease the current consumption. The representative agent would hence not invest in green capital when optimizing (1).

A.2 The maximisation problem for ignorant agents with two capital stocks

To show (11), consider maximising production within a single time step:

$$\max_{b_t^{(i)}, g_t^{(i)}} P_t^{(i)} = \left(P_t^{G^{(i)}} + P_t^{B^{(i)}} \right) \text{ such that } g_t^{(i)} + b_t^{(i)} = L_t^{(i)}$$

With $b_t^{(i)} = L_t^{(i)} - g_t^{(i)}$, the total production is

$$P_t^{(i)} = \left(G_t^{(i)} \right)^\alpha \left(\gamma_t g_t^{(i)} \right)^{1-\alpha} + \left(B_t^{(i)} \right)^\alpha \left(\beta_t \left(L_t^{(i)} - g_t^{(i)} \right) \right)^{1-\alpha}.$$

Its critical points can be obtained from

$$\frac{\partial P_t^{(i)}}{\partial g_t^{(i)}} = (1 - \alpha) \left(G_t^{(i)}\right)^\alpha \gamma_t^{1-\alpha} \left(g_t^{(i)}\right)^{-\alpha} - (1 - \alpha) \left(B_t^{(i)}\right)^\alpha \beta_t^{1-\alpha} \left(L_t^{(i)} - g_t^{(i)}\right)^{-\alpha} = 0.$$

Substituting back

$$(1 - \alpha) \left(G_t^{(i)}\right)^\alpha \gamma_t^{1-\alpha} \left(g_t^{(i)}\right)^{-\alpha} = (1 - \alpha) \left(B_t^{(i)}\right)^\alpha \beta_t^{1-\alpha} \left(b_t^{(i)}\right)^{-\alpha},$$

which means that for all t ,

$$\frac{g_t^{(i)}}{b_t^{(i)}} = \frac{G_t^{(i)}}{B_t^{(i)}} \left(\frac{\gamma_t}{\beta_t}\right)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}}.$$

Using (12), one can rewrite Equations (4) and (7) as

$$C_t^{(i)} = \left(B_t^{(i)}\right)^\alpha \left(\beta_t b_t^{(i)}\right)^{1-\alpha} \left(1 + \tau_t \frac{G_t^{(i)}}{B_t^{(i)}}\right) - I_G^{(i)} - I_B^{(i)} \quad (\text{A2})$$

$$C_{t+1}^{(i)} = \left(B_{t+1}^{(i)}\right)^\alpha \left(\beta_{t+1} b_{t+1}^{(i)}\right)^{1-\alpha} \left(1 + \tau_{t+1} \frac{G_{t+1}^{(i)}}{B_{t+1}^{(i)}}\right). \quad (\text{A3})$$

Note that these formulations of $C_t^{(i)}$ and $C_{t+1}^{(i)}$ do not make explicit the dependency of the future labour values on the investment decisions. This could be done by fully solving for $b_t^{(i)}$ instead of considering Equation 11:

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - \alpha) \left(G_t^{(i)}\right)^\alpha \gamma_t^{1-\alpha} \left(L_t^{(i)} - b_t^{(i)}\right)^{-\alpha} &= (1 - \alpha) \left(B_t^{(i)}\right)^\alpha \beta_t^{1-\alpha} \left(b_t^{(i)}\right)^{-\alpha} \\ \left(G_t^{(i)}\right)^{-1} \gamma_t^{-\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} \left(L_t^{(i)} - b_t^{(i)}\right) &= \left(B_t^{(i)}\right)^{-1} \beta_t^{-\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} b_t^{(i)} \\ B_t^{(i)} \beta_t^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} \left(L_t^{(i)} - b_t^{(i)}\right) &= G_t^{(i)} \gamma_t^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} b_t^{(i)} \\ B_t^{(i)} \beta_t^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} L_t^{(i)} &= \left(G_t^{(i)} \gamma_t^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} + B_t^{(i)} \beta_t^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}}\right) b_t^{(i)} \\ b_t^{(i)} &= \frac{B_t^{(i)} \beta_t^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} L_t^{(i)}}{G_t^{(i)} \gamma_t^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}} + B_t^{(i)} \beta_t^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}}} \end{aligned}$$

Then, through $B_{t+1}^{(i)}$, the investment I_B would also explicitly influence the future labour value $b_{t+1}^{(i)}$. However, the agent does not know the future technical progress values β_{t+1} and γ_{t+1} at the moment of the investment decision but will know these values at the point in time when the labour allocation has to be decided (in step $t + 1$). The future labour allocation will therefore most probably vary from the value computed here and therefore, we consider the more explicit knowledge about $b_{t+1}^{(i)}$ superfluous

at this point. The following considerations hence continue with the formulation of the consumption constraints in (A2) and (A3), for which the critical points that maximise utility are given by

$$\frac{\partial U^{(i)}}{\partial I_B^{(i)}} = -\frac{1}{C_t^{(i)}} + \frac{\rho}{C_{t+1}^{(i)}} \left(\frac{\beta_{t+1} b_{t+1}^{(i)}}{B_{t+1}^{(i)}} \right)^{1-\alpha} \left(\alpha + (\alpha - 1) \tau_{t+1} \frac{G_{t+1}^{(i)}}{B_{t+1}^{(i)}} \right) = 0 \quad (\text{A4})$$

$$\frac{\partial U^{(i)}}{\partial I_G^{(i)}} = -\frac{1}{C_t^{(i)}} + \frac{\rho \tau_{t+1}}{C_{t+1}^{(i)}} \left(\frac{\beta_{t+1} b_{t+1}^{(i)}}{B_{t+1}^{(i)}} \right)^{1-\alpha} = 0. \quad (\text{A5})$$

These equations can further be equated or each of them solved for the hidden terms I_B or I_G in C_t as well as in B_{t+1} and G_{t+1} within C_{t+1} , respectively. First, from (A4) = (A5), one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha + (\alpha - 1) \tau_{t+1} \frac{G_{t+1}^{(i)}}{B_{t+1}^{(i)}} &= \tau_1 & (\text{A6}) \\ \Rightarrow B_{t+1}^{(i)} &= \frac{\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1)}{\tau_{t+1} - \alpha} G_{t+1}^{(i)}, \end{aligned}$$

and substituting $B_{t+1}^{(i)} = (1 - \delta) + I_B^{(i)}$ and similarly for $G_{t+1}^{(i)}$,

$$\Rightarrow I_B^{(i)} = \frac{\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1)}{\tau_{t+1} - \alpha} \left((1 - \delta) G_t^{(i)} + I_G^{(i)} \right) - (1 - \delta) B_t^{(i)} \quad (\text{A7})$$

As (A5) looks simpler than (A4), we return to the former to solve for $I_G^{(i)}$. It can be rewritten as

$$C_{t+1}^{(i)} \left(B_{t+1}^{(i)} \right)^{1-\alpha} = \rho \tau_{t+1} \left(\beta_{t+1} b_{t+1}^{(i)} \right)^{1-\alpha} C_t^{(i)}$$

and substituting the consumption constraints (A2) and (A3), this is

$$\begin{aligned} \left(B_{t+1}^{(i)} \right)^{1-\alpha} \left(B_{t+1}^{(i)} \right)^{\alpha} \left(\beta_{t+1} b_{t+1}^{(i)} \right)^{1-\alpha} \left(1 + \tau_{t+1} \frac{G_{t+1}^{(i)}}{B_{t+1}^{(i)}} \right) &= \rho \tau_{t+1} \left(\beta_{t+1} b_{t+1}^{(i)} \right)^{1-\alpha} \left(P_t^{(i)} - I_B^{(i)} - I_G^{(i)} \right) \\ B_{t+1}^{(i)} + \tau_{t+1} G_{t+1}^{(i)} &= \rho \tau_{t+1} \left(P_t^{(i)} - I_B^{(i)} - I_G^{(i)} \right) \\ (1 - \delta) B_t^{(i)} + I_B^{(i)} + \tau_{t+1} \left((1 - \delta) G_t^{(i)} + I_G^{(i)} \right) &= \rho \tau_{t+1} \left(P_t^{(i)} - I_B^{(i)} - I_G^{(i)} \right). \end{aligned}$$

While this can be reordered as follows towards solving for $I_G^{(i)}$,

$$\tau_{t+1} I_G^{(i)} + \rho \tau_{t+1} I_G^{(i)} = \rho \tau_{t+1} P_t^{(i)} - (1 - \delta) B_t^{(i)} - \tau_{t+1} (1 - \delta) G_t^{(i)} - I_B^{(i)} (1 + \rho \tau_{t+1}),$$

the solution would contain an $I_B^{(i)}$ -term, leading to circular definitions. Hence we substitute (A7) at this point to get

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau_{t+1}I_G^{(i)} + \rho\tau_{t+1}I_G^{(i)} &= \rho\tau_{t+1}P_t^{(i)} - (1-\delta)B_t^{(i)} - \tau_{t+1}(1-\delta)G_t^{(i)} \\
&\quad - (1+\rho\tau_{t+1})\left(\frac{\tau_{t+1}(\alpha-1)}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}\left((1-\delta)G_t^{(i)} + I_G^{(i)}\right) - (1-\delta)B_t^{(i)}\right) \\
&= \rho\tau_{t+1}\left(P_t^{(i)} + (1-\delta)B_t^{(i)}\right) - \tau_{t+1}(1-\delta)G_t^{(i)} \\
&\quad - (1+\rho\tau_{t+1})\left(\frac{\tau_{t+1}(\alpha-1)}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}\left((1-\delta)G_t^{(i)} + I_G^{(i)}\right)\right) \\
I_G^{(i)} + \rho I_G^{(i)} &= \rho\left(P_t^{(i)} + (1-\delta)B_t^{(i)}\right) - (1-\delta)G_t^{(i)} - (1+\rho\tau_{t+1})\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}\left((1-\delta)G_t^{(i)} + I_G^{(i)}\right)\right)
\end{aligned}$$

as all terms had a factor τ_{t+1} . What remains is just further simplification of

$$\begin{aligned}
I_G^{(i)}\left(1+\rho+(1+\rho\tau_{t+1})\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}\right)\right) &= \rho\left(P_t^{(i)} + (1-\delta)B_t^{(i)}\right) - (1-\delta)G_t^{(i)} \\
&\quad - (1+\rho\tau_{t+1})\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}(1-\delta)G_t^{(i)}\right) \\
&= \rho\left(P_t^{(i)} + (1-\delta)B_t^{(i)}\right) - (1-\delta)G_t^{(i)}\left(1+(1+\rho\tau_{t+1})\frac{\alpha-1}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
1+\rho+(1+\rho\tau_{t+1})\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}\right) &= \frac{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha+\rho\tau_{t+1}-\rho\alpha+\alpha-1+\rho\tau_{t+1}\alpha-\rho\tau_{t+1}}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha} \\
&= \frac{\tau_{t+1}-\rho\alpha-1+\rho\tau_{t+1}\alpha}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha} = \frac{(\tau_{t+1}-1)(1+\rho\alpha)}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$1+(1+\rho\tau_{t+1})\left(\frac{\alpha-1}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}\right) = \frac{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha+\alpha-1+\rho\tau_{t+1}\alpha-\rho\tau_{t+1}}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha} = \frac{\tau_{t+1}(1-\rho+\rho\alpha)-1}{\tau_{t+1}-\alpha}$$

Hence,

$$I_G^{(i)} = \frac{\rho(\tau_{t+1}-\alpha)\left(P_t^{(i)} + (1-\delta)B_t^{(i)}\right) + (1-\delta)G_t^{(i)}[1-\tau_{t+1}(1-\rho+\rho\alpha)]}{(1+\rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1}-1)}$$

We can then write also $I_B^{(i)}$ explicitly by substituting $I_G^{(i)}$ in $I_B^{(i)}$,

$$I_B^{(i)} = \frac{\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1)}{\tau_{t+1} - \alpha} \left[(1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \tau_{t+1}(1 + \rho(\alpha - 1))}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \right) + \frac{\rho(\tau_{t+1} - \alpha) \left(P_t^{(i)} + (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)} \right)}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \right] - (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)}$$

To simplify the expression, use

$$\begin{aligned} \left(1 + \frac{1 - \tau_{t+1}(1 + \rho(\alpha - 1))}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \right) &= \frac{\tau_{t+1} - 1 + \alpha\rho\tau_{t+1} - \alpha\rho + 1 - \tau_{t+1} - \alpha\rho\tau_{t+1} + \rho\tau_{t+1}}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \\ &= \frac{\rho(\tau_{t+1} - \alpha)}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the brown investment is explicitly given by

$$\begin{aligned} I_B^{(i)} &= \frac{\rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1)(\tau_{t+1} - \alpha)}{\tau_{t+1} - \alpha} \left(\frac{(1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} + P_t^{(i)} + (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)}}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \right) - (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)} \\ &= \rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1) \left(\frac{(1 - \delta)(G_t^{(i)} + B_t^{(i)}) + P_t^{(i)}}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \right) - (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)} \\ &= (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)} \left(\frac{\rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1)}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} - 1 \right) + \frac{\rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1) \left(P_t^{(i)} + (1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} \right)}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \end{aligned}$$

We rewrite the first bracket

$$\frac{\rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1)}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} - 1 = \frac{\alpha\rho\tau_{t+1} - \rho\tau_{t+1} - \tau_{t+1} + 1 - \alpha\rho\tau_{t+1} + \alpha\rho}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} = \frac{-\rho\tau_{t+1} - \tau_{t+1} + 1 + \alpha\rho}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)}$$

Finally,

$$I_B^{(i)} = \frac{\rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1) \left[P_t^{(i)} + (1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} \right] + (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)}(1 + \alpha\rho - \tau_{t+1}(\rho + 1))}{(\tau_{t+1} - 1)(1 + \alpha\rho)}$$

If we sum these two investments, the original "ignorant" agent's investment for one capital stock is recovered:

$$\begin{aligned} I_B^{(i)} + I_G^{(i)} &= \frac{\rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1) \left(P_t^{(i)} + (1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} \right) + (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)}(1 - \tau_{t+1} - \rho\tau_{t+1} + \rho\alpha)}{(\tau_{t+1} - 1)(1 + \alpha\rho)} \\ &\quad + \frac{\rho(\tau_{t+1} - \alpha) \left(P_t^{(i)} + (1 - \delta)B_t^{(i)} \right) + (1 - \delta)G_t^{(i)} [1 - \tau_{t+1}(1 - \rho + \rho\alpha)]}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{P_t^{(i)} [\rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1) + \rho(\tau_{t+1} - \alpha)]}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \\
&\quad + \frac{(1 - \delta) \left(G_t^{(i)} [\rho\tau_{t+1}(\alpha - 1) + 1 - \tau_{t+1} + \rho\tau_{t+1} - \rho\tau_{t+1}\alpha] \right)}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \\
&\quad + \frac{(1 - \delta) \left(B_t^{(i)} [1 - \tau_{t+1} - \rho\tau_{t+1} + \rho\alpha + \rho(\tau_{t+1} - \alpha)] \right)}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \\
&= \frac{P_t^{(i)} [\rho\alpha(\tau_{t+1} - 1)] + (1 - \delta)(1 - \tau_{t+1}) \left(G_t^{(i)} + B_t^{(i)} \right)}{(1 + \rho\alpha)(\tau_{t+1} - 1)} \\
&= \frac{1}{1 + \rho\alpha} \left(\rho\alpha P_t^{(i)} - (1 - \delta) \left(G_t^{(i)} + B_t^{(i)} \right) \right)
\end{aligned}$$

A.3 Further detail on the opinion dynamics processes

The expected waiting time for all agents to switch to green – in a fully connected network – can be determined by a rather simple recursive consideration. Let k_x denote the expected waiting time for all agents switching to green when starting in state x , i.e. with x green agents. For our total number of 100 agents, note that $k_{100} = 0$, because when starting from 100 green agents, the waiting time for reaching 100 green agents is zero. Then consider $x = 99$, which is

$$\begin{aligned}
k_{99} &= 1 + P(X_{t+1} = 100 | X_t = 99) * k_{100} + P(X_{t+1} = 99 | X_t = 99) * k_{99} \\
&= 1 + 0 + \left(1 - \frac{100 - 99}{100} * \frac{99}{99} \right) * k_{99} = 1 + \left(1 - \frac{1}{100} \right) * k_{99} \\
k_{99} &= 100
\end{aligned}$$

because when making one step (counted in the first term), one may arrive at $x = 100$, from where the expected further waiting time is k_{100} , or remain at $x = 99$, from where it is k_{99} . Moving backwards in time, the expected waiting times for reaching 100 green agents can be computed in the same way for any $x \in \{20, \dots, 100\}$.

Next, one can generalize this procedure for computing the expected waiting times of arriving at any possible number y of green agents, always starting from the premise that the waiting time is zero when one has arrived at the point of interest and recursively computing backwards from $y - 1$ for all $x \leq y$. The results of these computations for $x = 20$ (as this is the initial number of green agents in the simulations performed) are seen in Figure 3b plotted for $y = 20, \dots, 100$ agents.

To compute the probabilities for the number of green agents increasing by 1 or 2 under the Majority rule with group size $r = 5$, note that one agent switches if one brown and four green agents are drawn, two switches in the case of two brown and three green agents. In drawing groups of agents, no agent can be drawn more than once

in the same time step and the order in which agents are drawn is irrelevant. Therefore,

$$P(X_{t+1} = x + 1 | X_t = x) = \frac{\binom{x}{4} * \binom{100-x}{1}}{\binom{100}{5}} = p_x$$

$$P(X_{t+1} = x + 2 | X_t = x) = \frac{\binom{x}{3} * \binom{100-x}{2}}{\binom{100}{5}} = q_x$$

$$P(X_{t+1} = x | X_t = x) = 1 - (p_x + q_x)$$

These values are shown in Figure 3a. The waiting times (shown in Figure 3b) for this case are computed as above based on these probabilities.

If we vary the group size, an important effect is that the possible combinations that induce agents to switch increase at odd numbers only. E.g., with $r = 5$, a switch occurs for two combinations (1 – 4 or 2 – 3 brown and green agents, respectively) and the same is true for $r = 6$ with 1 – 5 and 2 – 4, since 3 – 3 does not lead to a switch. Only for $r = 7$, a third possible combination arises (1 – 6, 2 – 5, 3 – 4). The corresponding probabilities are illustrated in Figure A1 which shows that the probability of not switching is generally lower for odd group sizes for most numbers of green agents and that among even as well as among odd group sizes initially (i.e., at 20 green agents) this probability is lower for smaller groups, the ordering changes after a majority of agents has switched to green.

Fig. A1: Probabilities of no switch for the majority rule with different group sizes.

Appendix B Selecting number of runs for the simulations results

For selecting the number of runs that will guarantee the statistical robustness of our results, we follow the framework proposed by [Hunter and Kelleher \(2020\)](#). To find the number of runs necessary to find a stable result for the model, we initially model

two social integration strategies. The social integration strategies are the standard voter model and the Majority rule with a discussion group of 5 agents. For each social integration strategy, we ran 2000 simulations keeping all the parameters, described in Table 1, constant. The seed we used at the beginning of each simulation to initialize the random number generator is 42.

In this work, the statistic we are interested in studying is the proportion of runs that led to a green transition in the economy. To define the green transition condition for a run, we used the definition given by Lamperti et al (2020): “A green transition has been reached when the economy’s green output reaches the 85% threshold and never fall back”. As the transition in the model is affected by the interaction patterns among the agents, not all the runs nor all the social integration strategies would lead to a transition.

To find the suitable number of simulations for this model, we separated the runs for each social integration strategy into different samples, i.e. the first sample contains the first 5 simulations, the second sample contains the first 10 simulations, the third sample contains the first 20 simulations and so on until we include all the runs in at least one sample. Then for each sample, we calculated the proportion of simulations that are above the green output threshold at the time step 110⁹, and the respective sample’s 95% confidence interval. Since the statistic is a proportion, we use it to compute the confidence interval around a single proportion \hat{p} of a sample of size s ,

$$\text{Confidence Interval} = \hat{p} \pm z \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}{s}}, \quad (\text{B8})$$

where $z = 1.96$ is a multiplier number that comes from the normal curve and determines the 95% level of confidence.

Table B1 presents selected values of the statistics and confidence intervals for different sample sizes from the 2,000 model simulation. In Table B1 we observe that the standard Voter dynamics don’t lead to a transition, therefore we use as a standpoint the Majority Rule for selecting the necessary number of runs. For the Majority rule the size of the confidence interval decreases as the size of the sample increases. When the length of the confidence interval is around 10% we need 350 runs. If we increase the sample size to 1280, the proportion of runs leading to a transition decreases from 35 to 32, also the confidence interval length decreases to 5% but the computing time increases. Therefore, we determine that 350 runs is the suitable number of runs for this model when we compute the proportion of runs leading to a green transition.

Appendix C Considerations for modelling carbon dioxide emissions

In the Agent-based model, the statistician is going to count the emissions of the brown farms. As a first approximation, we assume that the brown capital is carbon intensive and the green capital doesn’t generate emissions. For modelling the CO₂ emissions

⁹We choose 110 time steps such that we guarantee that at the end of the simulation, the economy’s green output never falls back.

Table B1: Proportions of runs leading to green transitions and its Confidence Intervals (CI) depending on the used social integration strategy

Social Integration Strategies	Sample Size (s)	Proportion (%)	Confidence Interval (CI)	CI length
Standard Majority rule	5	40.00	(-0.029, 0.829)	0.86
	100	34.00	(0.247, 0.433)	0.19
	350	35.14	(0.301, 0.401)	0.10
	640	32.97	(0.293, 0.366)	0.07
	1280	30.70	(0.282, 0.332)	0.05
2000	30.70	(0.287, 0.327)	0.04	
Standard Voter	5	0.00	(0.0, 0.0)	0.00
	100	0.00	(0.0, 0.0)	0.00
	350	0.00	(0.0, 0.0)	0.00
	640	0.00	(0.0, 0.0)	0.00
	1280	0.00	(0.0, 0.0)	0.00
2000	0.00	(0.0, 0.0)	0.00	

we use the equation presented in [Barrage and Nordhaus \(2023\)](#), without taking into account the land and non-abatable emissions.

$$\text{Em } CO_2 = \sigma(t)P_{B,t},$$

Where $P_{B,t}$ is the brown production at time step t , and $\sigma(t)$ is the carbon intensity at time step t . The yearly rate of carbon intensity according to ([Barrage and Nordhaus, 2023](#)) is $C_{yrate} = -1.5\%$. To compute the quarterly rate q of carbon intensity $\sigma(t)$ we do the following computations. We know that we can write the yearly carbon rate as follows

$$\frac{\sigma(t) - \sigma(t_0)}{\sigma(t_0)} = C_{yrate}$$

So after y time steps, where y indicates us how many time steps are in a year, the carbon intensity would be given by

$$\sigma(y * t) = \sigma(t_0)(1 - C_{yrate})$$

And $\sigma(t_0) = \frac{0.291tCO_2}{1000P_{B,0}}$ is given exogenously.

To know the evolution of the carbon intensity, we have to decide how to represent a year in terms of time steps. In this paper, we say that a one-time step corresponds to a quarter, i.e. that 4-time steps are one year in the model. First, we have to know the quarterly rate of carbon intensity q . We have that that four times the quarterly rate gives us the yearly carbon intensity, i.e.

$$q^4 = \sigma(y * t) \tag{C9}$$

Therefore, the quarterly rate is given by

$$q = [\sigma(t_0)(1 - C_{yrate})]^{1/4} \tag{C10}$$

To know the quarterly evolution of the carbon intensity, we use again the rate formula

$$\frac{\sigma(t+1) - \sigma(t)}{\sigma(t)} = q \tag{C11}$$

So, the carbon intensity at the next time step would be given by

$$\sigma(t+1) = \sigma(t)(1 + q) \tag{C12}$$

or by substituting q , we have that

$$\sigma(t+1) = \sigma(t)(1 + [\sigma(t_0)(1 - C_{yrate})]^{1/4}) \tag{C13}$$

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